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SUPER MoRRI – Scientific understanding and provision of an enhanced and robust monitoring system for RRI

D7.8 Executive summary of the final event

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
ORRI	Open and Responsible Research and Innovation
DG-RTD	Directorate-General Research and Innovation
CWTS	Centre for Science and Technology Studies
SwafS	Science with and for Society
M&E	Monitoring and evaluation

Executive Summary

With the ambition to actualise the knowledge produced during the SUPER MoRRI project with current movements and uncertainties surrounding research and innovation policy and their monitoring and evaluation, the SUPER MoRRI final event was designed to facilitate exchange. During a two day event in Brussels, project representatives and actors from research performing and funding organisations convened, facilitating discussions that largely revolved around two main themes: the affordances of monitoring and evaluation practices vis-à-vis ambitions of contemporary research and innovation policies and the translation of the intellectual heritage, values and resources from an era focusing on responsible research and innovation as a policy instrument to bettering science-society relations to current notions of open science and associated movements. There are various issues identified, from problematic instituted routines to translational issues between policy and practice. Overall, the final event, we think, fulfilled its purpose to both communicate the results from SUPER MoRRI and provide a moment to gather the associated community to make the knowledge matter for the kinds of uncertainties that European research and innovation policy faces today.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Scope and objectives of the deliverable

This deliverable aims at reporting on the SUPER MoRRI Final Event that took place in Saint-Gilles in Brussels on November 30th and December 1st, 2023. This report is structured around three main sections. Section one elaborates on general information on the event and rehearses the process that was followed to design an event that reflects the knowledge of SUPER MoRRI whilst at the same time making space for attunement with current policy issues around monitoring and evaluation. The second section takes a chronological approach to the different sessions that were held and briefly summarises the key points that either were made during presentations, the discussion or the interactive sessions that were held. Finally, the last section elaborates on the overall story that these observations, coupled with the SUPER MoRRI learnings, give rise to.

1.2. SUPER MoRRI origins

One of the key concerns that accompanied the design of the SUPER MoRRI final event from the beginning was a changed (science) policy environment than what the project was heralded into. Predominantly, this concerns the original institutional backing of ‘Responsible Research and Innovation’ (RRI) as a policy instrument to govern research and innovation promoted by the Directorate General Research and Innovation (DG-RTD), and attached ideas of monitoring and evaluation as developed in the preceding MoRRI project¹.

Additionally, throughout the project lifetime, the new European Commission framework programme Horizon Europe² and different movements within DG-RTD³ have resulted in a discontinuation of RRI as a policy, changing it into ‘mainstreaming of RRI aspects’ from the start of Horizon Europe in 2021 as per the previously established ideas.

As an umbrella project that also had a supporting role in relation to other RRI-related projects that were funded under the Science with and for Society programme⁴, the role of SUPER MoRRI changed considerably. Of course, this led to reflections with regard to the planning of the final event as well, which we elaborate in section 6.

¹ See the summary report on the project “Monitoring the evolution and benefits of responsible research and innovation in Europe” (2018) via following link: <https://super-morri.eu/download/155/morri-deliverables/3341/morri-d13.pdf>

² See a breakdown of new funding priorities in European research and innovation via following link: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/horizon-europe-work-programmes_en#work-programmes-under-horizon-europe

³ See (Owen et al., 2021)

⁴ See (European Commission et al., 2020)

It also affected the SUPER MORRI Monitoring and Evaluation Framework, and the concepts, principles and findings that are communicated by SUPER MoRRI, moving from RRI as the central organising device to a more diversified array of terms that can be understood as an associated family of movements and approaches reconfiguring science-society relations, including: Open and responsible research and innovation more generally, as well as responsible research assessment, open science and citizen science, but also transformative research and innovation, amongst other movements whose core concern are reconfiguring the relations between science and society to more democratic and beneficial ways.

2. BACKGROUND INFORMATION

2.1. Preparation and process

The organisation of the SUPER MoRRI Final Event was led by the team at CWTS from Leiden University (ULEI), starting in November 2022. The preparation was divided into a work package that concerned the logistical and organisational properties of the final event, such as the booking of the location, communications and budgetary matters; and the content-related work package that shaped what story should guide the SUPER MoRRI final event.

We want to focus on the latter in this section. As introduced before, the changing role of SUPER MoRRI resulted in the careful consideration of how the results on monitoring and evaluation of RRI would be told during the event. In order to address these issues in a way that allows for collective deliberation, the team at CWTS set up a working group with representatives from all work packages that met monthly from January until July 2023.

These working group meetings served the CWTS team to not overlook important considerations or certain actors, allowing to collectively shape the final event. This materialized in a number of assets, including:

- Principles that guided the choices regarding the location of the event.
- Definition of the questions and interests that different audiences have.
- How the SUPER MoRRI team will present its knowledge vis-à-vis these questions.
- A list of initial invitees that spanned three different ‘actor groups’:
 - o Related to ‘Policy and Learning’ actors who primarily are engaged with research and innovation policy and associated questions (e.g. monitoring).
 - o Related to RRI ‘Peers and Reflection’ actors who represent a lot of the community of SwafS-related project representatives that enact RRI in a more academic sense in reflection of the governance of research and innovation.
 - o Related to ‘Translation and Action’ actors who we delineated as actors who are not directly involved in questions about monitoring and evaluation, or for that matter research and innovation at all, but nonetheless implicated in research and innovation practices where the learnings from SUPER MoRRI can be considered relevant (e.g. in Green Deal related research projects).

Each actor group was appointed two SUPER MoRRI internal ‘subject coordinators’ and one external peer who has engaged with broader reflections of RRI before. The peers’ role was to enable a soft process of triangulation of expected problematics that motivate our audience’s presence. Please find an overview of the three strands and corresponding actors below:

	Policy & Learning <i>Lead: Ralf Lindner & Gema Revuelta</i> <i>RRI-Peer: Angela Simone</i>	Peers & Reflection <i>Lead: Ingeborg Meijer & Steven Flipse</i> <i>RRI-Peer: Dani Shanley</i>	Translation & Action <i>Lead: Roger Strand & Erich Griessler</i> <i>RRI-Peer: Angela Guimarães Pereira</i>
Question <i>The central problematisation that motivate the audience to engage.</i>	<i>How can we serve current policy issues based on SuMo knowledge?</i>	<i>What have we [as a community of people caring about R&I] learned and who can benefit?</i>	<i>How can SUPER MoRRI support other domains?</i>
Audience <i>Who is to be invited?</i>	<i>Policy allies on governing R&I well</i>	<i>Peers who engage(d) in thinking about RRI</i>	<i>Actors we believe need to / know about what implications our knowledge has on their way of working.</i>
Ambition <i>What do we want to achieve?</i>	<i>Facilitate and support consorted thinking on (O)RRI practices</i>	<i>Revisit the ambition of 'collective stewardship' under the backdrop of OS, RRA and so on.</i>	<i>Translate our insights into actionable outputs, together.</i>

Table 1: Thematic strands to support the development of the final event

We do want to mention that unfortunately, only little invitations sent out to actors that were identified for the ‘Translation & Action’ group were accepted. This led to the internal decision to focus on the other two actor groups and involve Ângela Guimarães Pereira (Joint Research Centre: Competence Centre on Participation and Deliberative Democracy) in relation to the concerns raised in the other two strands, as well.

Finally, after these invitations were extended, the registration process was opened up to the public with the support of communication channels of the European Commission.

After monthly consultations until July 2023, the preparation of the event went into an execution phase, translating the ideas shared and agreed upon during the meetings into an event with defined roles and responsibilities, supported by the entirety of SUPER MoRRI.

2.2. Location

In consideration of the underlying questions, audiences and ambitions in relation to them, the group noticed a pattern that, perhaps unsurprisingly, the majority of actors is located in the wider Brussels area. As Brussels can be reached relatively well by most consortium members by rail, we decided to host the event in Brussels. In an attempt to underline the non-neutrality of knowledge and its production, we refrained from renting a traditional conference centre and instead rented a physical space in a cultural centre in Saint-Gilles, namely the ‘Pianofabriek’ (Rue du Fortstraat 35, 1060 St-Gillis).

In total, 70 participants registered before the event registration was made public and 51 participants, excluding the SUPER MoRRI consortium members, participated during the event.

3. SUMMARIES

With this basis, we developed the programme⁵ for this two-day event, pursuing two goals: (1) to communicate and deliberate on the results of the SUPER MoRRI projects, in particular the results from the main data vehicles⁶. Another goal was to (2) making the space for interactive sessions in order to actualize SUPER MoRRI results with contemporary policy issues as a way to engage in translational work exactly given the shifted research and innovation policy context that SUPER MoRRI moved with. In the following section, we want to describe the sessions and give credit to those who designed them.

Table 2: Session summaries

Title Author(s)	Description
Welcome Ralf Lindner, Fraunhofer ISI, Irina Elena Tiron, REA	In this opening session of the SUPER MoRRI Final Event, the project coordinator Ralf Lindner and the corresponding project officer to the SUPER MoRRI, Irina Elena Tiron, welcomed the participants. They elaborated on how the policy landscape surrounding RRI changed in the years since SUPER MoRRI’s inception and what strategies the project employed to respond to these. The movement from Horizon 2020 to Horizon Europe incorporates, for them, a continued incorporation of the values that are associated with RRI in structured program requirements as a criterion for evaluation, but also a principle for research and innovation practice.
Setting the Scene Danielle Shanley, Maastricht University	We explicitly requested Danielle Shanley to provide a macroscopic view on the intellectual origins of RRI and her reflections on its policy-related enactment as a scholar whose most formative time has been during a time with immense policy attention on the RRI project. Drawing on work from science and technology studies, she shifted the analytical focus to the social and material movements that contributed to making RRI matter in the first place. Offering historical comparison, she presented RRI as originating firmly in the governance of emerging technologies with a strong commitment to the project of democratization of research and innovation whilst fulfilling a collectively moral imperative of answering societal needs. And whilst the RRI project for many seemed to seize to exist, she advocated for challenging assumptions, thinking about

⁵ See the full programme in Appendix 9.2

⁶ See D2.4 Annotated methodological procedure report via following link: <https://super-morri.eu/download/153/findings-and-deliverables/5467/d-2-4-annotated-methodological-procedures-report-3.pdf>

Title Author(s)	Description
	<p>the mechanics of change, expansion of the community’s horizons, the fostering of cooperation and care and, in her words ‘to keep calm and carry on’ – irrespective of what new instrument for the democratic governance of research and innovation emerges next in Brussels’ policy realities. With this, she heralded the event with an optimistic and pragmatic perspective, grounding theoretically as well as historically the actors present at the event.</p>
<p>History and learnings</p> <p>Moderation by Gema Revuelta, University of Pompeu Fabra:</p> <p>Ralf Lindner, Fraunhofer ISI; Thomas Kjedadger Ryan, Aarhus University; Shauna Stack, IHS; Carolina Llorente, UPF; Anestis Amanatidis, CWTS</p>	<p>This session took a panel-interview format where SUPER MoRRI partners representing different work packages summarized (1) what work they led, (2) key results and (3) what they would have done differently. Thomas Kjedadger Ryan reflected on these from the point of view of the secondary and primary data collection through the country correspondent network that was led by Aarhus University, Shauna Stack on the case studies and further conceptualization of RRI benefits and alternative ‘impact journeys’. Carolina Llorente focused on the involvement of a wide network of global SUPER MoRRI partners that were involved to inquire in the respective countries that they represented and the so-called ‘international satellite partners’, which were a global group of (research) actors to reflect on and triangulate research findings from the SUPER MoRRI project in relation to radically different science systems. Anestis Amanatidis spoke of the experiences in connecting to and learning from a wide group of RRI project representatives. In monthly conversations, these representatives were engaged in presentations, discussions and focus groups to learn from experimentations with (responsible) research practices and reflect on their monitoring and evaluation in particular⁷</p>
<p>SUPER MoRRI Exhibition</p> <p><i>PROMISE Portal</i></p> <p>André Brasil, CWTS; Thomas Kjedadger Ryan, Aarhus University</p> <p><i>Case studies</i></p>	<p>The so-called ‘SUPER MoRRI Exhibition’ was dedicated to the free exploration and critical inquiry of the event’s participants with regards to the different streams of work in SUPER MoRRI. To allow for individuals to engage primarily with those who led the development of monitoring and evaluation tools (self-assessment tool, PROMISE portal) and data collection exercises that informed them (individual researcher survey, case studies), booths were put up that exhibited the work done. These booths took different forms:</p>

⁷ See D7.7 Summary report of exchange with SwafS funded projects related to RRI. The SUPER MoRRI RRI ecosystems - doing RRI together (available at: <https://super-morri.eu/findings/>)

Title Author(s)	Description
<p>Erich Griessler, Shauna Stack, IHS Vienna</p> <p><i>Self-assessment tool</i></p> <p>Steven Flipse, Emad Yaghmaei, TU Delft</p> <p><i>Individual researcher survey</i></p> <p>Hendrik Berghäuser Susanne Bühner-Topçu, Fraunhofer ISI</p>	<p><i>Individual Researcher Survey</i>: consisted of printed data sheets that depicted a limited range of results from the questionnaire, hosted by colleagues from Fraunhofer ISI.</p> <p><i>Self-assessment tool</i>: consisted of a computer-setup where participants could browse the prototype of the self-assessment tool and engage in conversation about it with colleagues from the TU Delft.</p> <p><i>PROMISE Portal</i>: also consisted of a demo of the working prototype of the PROMISE portal and was hosted by colleagues from SIMAVI.</p> <p><i>Case studies</i>: consisted of different ‘audio stations’, where participants could listen to the case authors describing their work; as well as printed summaries of the analysis done by colleagues at the Institute for Advanced Studies in Vienna.⁸</p>
<p>World Café</p> <p>Moderated by Ingeborg Meijer, CWTS:</p> <p>Angela Simone, Mika Nieminen, Carmen Fenollosa (REINFORCING)</p> <p>Stephane Berghmans (EUA)</p> <p>Fereshteh Rafieian, UNESCO</p> <p>Ângela Guimarães Pereira, (JRC DEMOS)</p> <p>Erzsébet Toth Czifra (CoARA)</p>	<p>One of the more interactive sessions during the SUPER MoRRI final event was the organisation of a World Café session with representatives from organisations that lead much of the contemporary developments in relation to monitoring and evaluation in and of science policy in Europe.</p> <p>These include the European University Association, the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment, UNESCO Open Science Unit, the Competence Centre on Participation and Deliberative Democracy of the Joint Research Centre and SUPER MoRRI’s successor project under Horizon Europe, REINFORCING.</p> <p>The World Café was of importance insofar as it was the main vehicle for those organisations to ask the questions that motivate their work in relation to monitoring and evaluation and RRI. It also set the tone for discussions that followed on day two of the event.</p> <p>During the session, five groups would migrate from table to table in given time slots, allowing the hosts of the tables, who represented the different organisations, ask their questions and thereby host ‘mini-focus groups’ with the participants of the final event.</p> <p>In preparation, the organizing colleagues had facilitated a joint meeting with all of the representatives to exchange over the kinds of questions that they would like to ask, introducing the scope and purpose of the session.</p> <p>The guiding questions per table were:</p> <p>European University Association:</p>

⁸ See Appendix 1

Title Author(s)	Description
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>What are your recommendations and ideas on how to implement the results of SUPER MoRRI in universities?</i> - <i>As EUA gathers Rectors and Vice-Rectors, how would you convince them of the strategic importance of RRI, and why should they care?</i> - <i>Similarly, but operationally this time, how can we do the same with research managers and administrators?</i> - <i>In both cases, what are opportunities that could help?</i> <p>Summary: For EUA the value of the RRI work by SUPER MoRRI very much lies in the translation of the findings into recommendations on implementation and practicalities. Who should do what, how and when? This concerns, for example, how the self-assessment tool can be realised as part of assessments. Also the SUPER MoRRI policy briefs and the primary data collected are highly relevant but, again, need to be actualised. Furthermore, reviewing the role of research funders in relation to ‘incentivising’ new practices and how resources from SUPER MoRRI can help in this process were addressed. The resources can work as a way to raise awareness around the cultural change so often highlighted in science policy, as the evidence describes this very point in time.</p> <p>Coalition for Advancing Responsible Research Assessment:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>How can we move from research assessment to academic career assessment?</i> - <i>How can we include a diversity of transversal skills in the assessment?</i> - <i>What prevents RPOs of appropriately crediting RRI practices?</i> - <i>And if we do want to focus on innovation: What skills are of particular interest to support innovation?</i> <p>Summary: Focusing on what is being valued in specific epistemic cultures and working on ways to capture these values is key to ‘responsible’ assessment practices. Research funders seem to have a dominant position in contributing to the systemic changes needed. Nonetheless, concerns exist about what career levels these reforms are for. Do senior position researchers who have a stronger voice in these reforms also benefit most of it? Simultaneously, there was a broad agreement that publication-driven assessment practices are not sustainable. However, narratives, stories and qualitative indicators are neither easy to produce nor cheap to maintain in a working science system. Quantitative data on the other hand is</p>

Title Author(s)	Description
	<p>much more accessible and thus predominantly used. In order to incentivise change, there is a clear role of research funders to act on recent developments and institute responsible funding routines that assessment practices. This transition comes with both a cultural change but also in the logics that drive the management of research and innovation. Learning needs to be facilitated bottom-up and evidenced.</p> <p>UNESCO Open Science:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>What should we take or leave for M&E at global level from Europe?</i> - <i>How to capture the diversity of open science practices?</i> - <i>How can we extend SUPER MoRRI to the global level?</i> - <i>How can the lessons learned from Super MoRRI be integrated into the global monitoring of Open Science, with a particular focus on promoting equity and capturing the diversity of science landscapes worldwide?</i> <p>Summary: Comparison does not afford the description of diverse realities. These are two conflicting goals of monitoring. Qualitative indicators, stories and narratives seem to afford the requirements of responsible monitoring. ‘What open science tries to achieve’ should be monitored, not openness in and of itself. Beware of callous properties of open access: may exacerbate injustices, for example not all institutions can afford to pay publishing fees. Also, the idea of a global picture of open science should be let go of, as vastly different realities can co-exist. Focus on local levels seem more constructive to the goal of monitoring, then grouping similar regions or countries that have some kind of commonality. Additionally, language plays an important role as well. Focusing solely on English research and innovation realities negatively complicates open science efforts. If inclusivity is to be taken seriously, awareness-raising is crucial, and there need to be support mechanisms developed and maintained for organisations. This is especially so with regards to the monitoring of practices that are not easily quantifiable as embraced by UNESCO. There seems to be a big learning opportunity requires from SUPER MoRRI knowledge.</p> <p>JRC CC on Participation and Deliberative Democracy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>What do we learn from SUPER MoRRI on the strategy and implementation of participatory practices and engagement?</i>

Title Author(s)	Description
	<p><i>How strongly are these practices embedded across Europe, are there specific patterns?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>What do we need to carry on as regards participatory practices and deliberative democracy to the future policy negotiations in the context of ERA?</i> <p>Summary: The discussion hosted by the Competence Centre for Participation and Deliberative Democracy (JRC) was an effort to collect insights from the participants on problematic observations in the context of participatory knowledge production. Whilst the rationale for participation is clear and advocated for through many intellectual movements in the past 40 years, making participation work in settings of knowledge production remains problematic. Especially in a political environment that is increasingly right-leaning, the question of participation seems more important than ever. One such observation was the perceived problems that become prioritised in research and whose issues and problems are being taken up by research and innovation, especially when it comes to legitimising local problems and enrolling local knowledge producing institutions to help resolve these problems. The (European) science system is, in this sense, not geared towards problems of local communities. Another issue was what ‘infrastructural’ properties of knowledge production can accommodate translation across (social, epistemic, cultural, etc.) differences. There is a strong need to actively disempower instituted routines that constrain participation.</p> <p>REINFORCING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>The transition from RRI to Open and Responsible R&I (ORRI) practices still builds heavily on the RRI knowledge base. How can the knowledge base be practically organized to support ORRI enablers?</i> - <i>Categories to sort out ORRI resources & actors’ perspectives to categorize ORRI resources?</i> - <i>PROMISE portal and cross-cutting resources and their integration in the REINFORCING platform/OS</i> <p>Summary: The main objective for the World Café session organised by the REINFORCING project was to get input or suggestions for categorising and making sense of the resources, materials and tools that are going to be collated at the REINFORCING ‘OneStopSource’ for open and responsible research and innovation in Europe. This was of particular importance as REINFORCING seems to be considered a successor to the SUPER MoRRI project. Next to the</p>

Title Author(s)	Description
	taxonomy of the platform, there was also a discussion as to how the SUPER MoRRI data, through the PROMISE portal, may be integrated.
Reflections and Check-out <i>Roger Strand, University of Bergen</i>	One of the key tenets of the SUPER MoRRI final event design was the actualization of SUPER MoRRI knowledge with contemporary issues. Beyond choices for the design of the contents, we also wanted to keep the programme receptive to new knowledge. This session was dedicated to this purpose, where Roger Strand facilitated a discussion that allowed participants to reflect on the first day of the event to account for during the second day. This plenary discussion rehearsed concerns about translation from RRI to ORRI and especially about the importance for maintaining the networks that were built in the era of the SwafS programme under Horizon2020. Keeping these networks alive also means the maintenance of tacit knowledge and its incorporation into current movements in Horizon Europe. The World Café thereby enabled a refreshment of the ideas that circulated and allowed to mobilise specific results into conversation with current actors, as such making it itself an attempt to translate SUPER MoRRI knowledge. Furthermore, it was stressed that it is important for an identity to be maintained that acts as a mesh for this intellectual community.
Reflections Day 1 & Mentimeter <i>Gema Revuelta, UPF Ralf Lindner and Hendrik Berghäuser, Fraunhofer ISI</i>	In this beginning session, results were shown from a polling activity during the SUPER MoRRI exhibition that compared the expectations of the participants to the actual results of the individual researcher survey based on the similar questions. Furthermore, the second day was opened by summarizing key impressions from the day before. At this point, please refer to the previous summaries, as this description would be rehearsing the same points.
Horizon open and responsible research and innovation: the REINFORCING project <i>Angela Simone, REINFORCING</i>	As a key project succeeding SUPER MoRRI in the new framework programme Horizon Europe by the European Commission, Angela Simone, who is coordinating it, introduced its scope, aims and plans and gathered feedback regarding SUPER MoRRI questions and learnings that apply specifically to the context of the REINFORCING project. In particular, this discussion was about the information structure. In general, REINFORCING will allocate cascade funding to projects especially in areas where there are weaknesses in the implementation of RRI. The project aims at creating a virtual platform for RRI and open science-related information and tools, which functions as an open resource and information service especially for REINFORCING-financed projects. The platform will include tools inherited from the RRI Tools platform, new tools developed by other projects (including the ones to be developed with the support of the project’s cascading grants), and training modules.

Title Author(s)	Description
Open and Responsible R&I in the EU: European Commission perspective <i>Georgios Papanagnou, DG-RTD, European Commission</i>	<p>Georgios Papanagnou, the corresponding policy officer to RRI in the Directorate General Research and Innovation, reflected on current R&I policy developments and ambitions in relation to RRI. Furthermore, Georgios Papanagnou also reflected on monitoring and evaluation of the R&I ambitions under Horizon Europe. In this presentation, open science assumed a key tenet in the translation of RRI into contemporary R&I policy. RRI values are distributed across regulatory and programmatic aims in Horizon Europe and requirements stress the connection between open science and the proposed plans. Furthermore, Georgios Papanagnou elaborated on the European Commission’s commitments to create support structures that allow for the ‘open and responsible’ conduit of research activities, such as the European Open Science Cloud, but also the rethinking assessment practices through the Coalition of Advancing Research Assessment.</p>
PROMISE Portal <i>Richard Woolley, Ingenio Andrei Alexandrescu, Claudiu Pertroi, SIMAVI</i> Thomas Kjedager Ryan, Shauna Stack, Hendrik Berghäuser, Steven Flipse	<p>This practical session was dedicated to the demonstration of the working prototype of the PROMISE portal (www.promise4era.eu), which will synthesise the data collected throughout the SUPER MoRRI project lifetime, allow for users to browse and export data. The difference between this session and the SUPER MoRRI Exhibition is that the latter was focused on the process surrounding the PROMISE portal creation, whilst this dedicated session was for the actual demonstration of use. During this demonstration, the different data vehicles that informed the portal were described by the respective SUPER MoRRI partners, including the research on research funding organisations (Richard Woolley), the study on research performing organizations (Thomas Kjedager Ryan), the individual researcher survey (Hendrik Berghäuser), the case studies (Shauna Stack) and the self-assessment tool (Steven Flipse) that is an integral element to the PROMISE portal.</p>
Lessons and Perspectives Ângela Guimarães Pereira, JRC (DEMOS); Ellen-Marie Forsberg, NORSUS; Michael Bernstein, Austrian Institute of Technology (not present)	<p>In a panel-interview format, this session was dedicated to gathering the thoughts and reflections of invited guests and advisory board members. Unfortunately, Michael Bernstein couldn’t attend the final event due to sickness.</p> <p>For Ângela Guimarães Pereira, the guiding question during this event was about the stories of public participation in knowledge production processes that became visible. From her perspective, working at a research organisation that informs European policy, she was particularly interested in dynamics around citizen science-related communities and the politics of participatory settings. Whilst SUPER MoRRI didn’t focus on emerging communities around citizen science per se, the case studies from Work Package 5 were of particular interest. She advocated for participation and inclusion, and in reflection to the discontinuation of</p>

Title Author(s)	Description
	<p>the RRI instrument in and of itself presented a view that understands participation and engagement, both dear to RRI, as continuous values in contemporary European research and innovation policy.</p> <p>As advisory board member, Ellen-Marie Forsberg cast a more critical view on her observations surrounding SUPER MoRRI. She focused her reflections on the operationalisation of responsibility in the data collection vehicles of SUPER MoRRI. In particular, she brought forth and stressed RRI's valuing of process-oriented aspects of research and innovation, namely anticipation, reflexivity, inclusion and responsiveness⁹. In so doing, she also made a point about directing more attention to the political economy in which RRI came to matter to ensure that a tendency for inward-orientation in the 'RRI ecosystem' would be addressed properly. Especially so with regards to the changed research and innovation policy landscape of the European Commission.</p>
Spoken word Jackie Ashkin	<p>In order to close the two-day event with a more reflective note, Jackie Ashkin¹⁰ performed her piece that she wrote for the SUPER MoRRI Final Event. As both an artist and STS scholar, the message of the piece was a reminder about the 'why' normative research and innovation policies; and more widely why science-society relations, especially pointed out by the 'with and for' of SUPER MoRRI's funding programme, exist. She puts this in contrast in a place where much of the discussion gravitates around the question of how to make RRI work in local research and innovation contexts, grounding the participants before concluding the event.</p>

⁹ See Stilgoe, J., Owen, R., & Macnaghten, P. (2013). Developing a framework for responsible innovation. *Research Policy*, 42(9), 1568–1580. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2013.05.008>

¹⁰ Find more about her work on her website: <https://www.jackieashkin.com/spokenword>

4. CONCLUSION

There is no single story to summarise the diversity of considerations and issues, but also approaches to problematic observations at the SUPER MoRRI final event. Nonetheless, there are some prominent aspects that recurred across different sessions that both confirm already-existing knowledge as e.g. produced in the SUPER MoRRI studies and events, but also relate directly to ongoing developments in (European) science policy. Below, we want to briefly touch on these and refer to reports and other dedicated projects that are caring for these issues.

4.1. Affordances of monitoring and evaluation

One dominant tension across most contributions during the event emerges from the limited affordances of current devices of monitoring and evaluation vis-à-vis the kinds of ambitions that contemporary research and innovation policies, including RRI and open science, lay out.

One such aspect arises in ambitions that open up knowledge production processes to diverse publics. Whilst the involvement of e.g. non-governmental organisations and other actor groups promises a sense of inclusion and science that rests upon democratic values, dominant practices in science, including funding practices, may act callously against such ambition in and of itself¹¹.

Especially important with regard to the Horizon Europe policy focus on ‘institutional changes’¹², the second aspect scrutinises how organisational routines disable the translation from policy to actual research practice; even though the very organisations might have already adopted policies pertaining to ambitions of open and responsible research and innovation. This observation is underlined by SUPER MoRRI findings that there are perceived barriers for practices such as public engagement, like a lack of institutional incentives.¹³

It follows that there is increasing pressure for monitoring and evaluation practices and devices to become more diversified in the kinds of aspects that they are (trying to; and actually can) monitor and evaluate. This includes a recognition of the diversity of contributions and careers in research, a move from quantitative indicators as shortcuts for scientific quality to contextualised, qualitative-quantitative configurations of indicators used responsibly¹⁴.

¹¹ See D5.4: Analytical Synthesis Report; see case ‘Ethics in AI’ and ‘Transdisciplinary Research Funding’. See also summary of World Café session hosted by JRC DEMOS and D2.3: Second Responsible Research and Innovation monitoring report. See also the summary for the session ‘Lessons and Perspectives’ (available at: <https://super-morri.eu/findings/>)

¹² See summary of ‘Horizon open and responsible research and innovation: the REINFORCING project’ by Angela Simone and ‘Open and Responsible R&I in the EU: European Commission perspective’ by Georgios Papanagnou.

¹³ See D5.4: Analytical Synthesis Report; see case ‘Gendered eco-innovation’; see Figure 5 on perception of barriers for RRI practices. See also D2.3: Second Responsible Research and Innovation monitoring report (available at: <https://super-morri.eu/findings/>).

¹⁴ In SUPER MoRRI, the terms ‘credible contextualisation’ and ‘responsible quantification’ try to describe these properties of what became known as ‘responsible’ monitoring and evaluation practices. For an overview, see <https://super-morri.eu/responsible-approach-to-monitoring-rri/>

More aspects emerged in the discussion of monitoring and evaluation in the World Café, especially in relation to the monitoring of open science following the UNESCO Recommendations on Open Science¹⁵. Furthermore, concerns were raised in relation to research(er) assessment in the contexts of normative research and innovation policies¹⁶.

Finally, the European Commission also presented what specific support instruments on a European level are set up to 'enable' the transition to a monitoring and assessment culture that attends to these ambitions. This includes, for instance, the Coalition for Reforming Research Assessment¹⁷ and the European Open Science Cloud¹⁸, as well as dedicated project, such as GraspOS¹⁹. On a programme level, it was presented how criteria for monitoring and evaluation pertaining to values and principles of responsible research and innovation became translated as (part of) the funding criteria in Horizon Europe proposal evaluations²⁰.

4.2. Translation of responsible research and innovation

The second dominant tension that occupied the participants was the translation of RRI into contemporary research and innovation policies. As described in the introduction, SUPER MoRRI represents (one of the) last SwafS-funded projects under Horizon2020 – the dedicated funding programme researching, promoting and experimenting with RRI. Being aware of the changed policy landscape, the question came up to what extent the contemporary research and innovation policies actually attend to the principles and values, but especially the knowledge produced in a decade of RRI research.

There were some concerns raised in that regard. The first concerns questions of participation and engagement in research and innovation as a key tenet of responsibility in research and innovation praxis. These questions were often raised vis-à-vis current experiences of narrow interpretations of open science that focus on the dissemination of research outputs as scientific virtue. The critique therein was that a narrow focus dismisses RRI's attention to research and innovation praxis²¹. Furthermore, even if participation is seriously considered, ensuring epistemic justice in participatory

¹⁵ See UNESCO Open Science summary of World Café session; see also the associated document: UNESCO. (2021). UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science. UNESCO. doi.org/10.54677/MNMMH8546

¹⁶ See footnote 14.

¹⁷ See www.coara.eu or read the full text of the agreement [here](#).

¹⁸ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Jones, S., Abramatic, J., European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) strategic implementation plan, Jones, S.(editor), Abramatic, J.(editor), Publications Office, 2019, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/202370>

¹⁹ GraspOS is an EOSC-funded project that develops tools and services for the promotion of open science practices in monitoring and evaluation practices. For further assets in this intersection, see Deliverable D2.1 "OS-aware RRA approaches landscape report": <https://zenodo.org/records/8301792>

²⁰ See summary of session Open and Responsible R&I in the EU: European Commission perspective by Georgios Papanagnou, DG-RTD, European Commission

²¹ See Stilgoe, J., Owen, R., & Macnaghten, P. (2013). Developing a framework for responsible innovation. *Research Policy*, 42(9), 1568–1580. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2013.05.008>; this was also highlighted by Ângela Guimarães Pereira, JRC (DEMOS) during the 'Lessons and Perspectives' panel (see summary).

knowledge production remains a largely understudied issue. Both these observations stress the expressed need for a continued social identity to maintain RRI's intellectual heritage without the institutional support structures of the European Commission. Existing structures, including the dedicated Journal of Responsible Innovation, thus can become important facilitators.

Finally, multiple references were made to a developing strand of RRI literature that treats translation as the making of associations in differing contexts. This was stressed strongly by Danielle Shanley's presentation, but also emerges as dedicated literature scrutinising properties of and the role of monitoring and evaluation in the translation of RRI ^{22, 23}. This perspective is particularly useful in scrutinising existing institutional structures and organisational routines in attempts to make governance structures support such translation.

²² See Holtrop, T., Meijer, I., Otero-Hermida, P., Amanatidis, A., Buongiovanni, C., Casale, D., Colonnello, C., Deserti, A., Feudi, F., Hartmann, A., Hörlesberger, M., Ipolyi, I. M., Nguyen, N., Nieminen, M., Quinti, G., Ravn, T., Rizzo, F., Schmittinger, F., Steinhaus, N., ... Yagmaei, E. (2022). Evaluative conversations: Translating between diverse stakeholders in regional RRI projects. *fteval - Austrian Platform for Research and Technology Policy Evaluation*. <https://doi.org/10.22163/fteval.2022.544>

²³ Völker, T., Mazzonetto, M., Slaattelid, R., & Strand, R. (2023). Translating tools and indicators in territorial RRI. *Frontiers in Research Metrics and Analytics*, 7, 1038970. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frma.2022.1038970>

5. Appendix 1

5.1. Overview of case studies

5.2. Programme

Programme 01.12.2023

Walk-In, coffee and tea
09:00-09:15

Reflections Day 1 & Mentimeter
09:15-09:30
Gema Revuelta, UPF
Ralf Lindner & Hendrik Berghäuser, Fraunhofer ISI

Horizon Open and Responsible Research and Innovation. The REINFORCING Project
09:30-10:00
Angela Simone, REINFORCING

Open and Responsible R&I in the EU: European Commission Perspective
10:00-10:30
Georgios Papanagnou, DG-RTD, European Commission

Break: 10:30-10:45

PROMISE Portal
10:45-12:00
André Brasil, CWTS
Richard Woolley, INGENIO
Andrei Alexandrescu & Claudiu Pertroi, SIMAVI

Lunch: 12:00-13:00

Lessons and Perspectives
13:00-13:45
Angela Guimarães Pereira, JRC (DEMOS)
Ellen-Marie Forsberg, NORSUS
Michael Bernstein, Austrian Institute of Technology

Discussion in Plenum
13:45-14:45
Moderation by Roger Strand, University of Bergen

Moving Forward: Summary and Impressions
14:45-15:00
Steven Flipse, TU Delft

Closing Final Event
15:00-15:15
Ralf Lindner, Fraunhofer ISI

Spoken word
15:15-15:30
Jackie Ashkin

Project Partners:

Fraunhofer ISI, UNIVERSITY OF BERGEN, ingenio, Institut für Mikrotechnik Elektronik Informationstechnik (IME), CWTS, AARHUS UNIVERSITY, upf | Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, SIMAVI, TU Delft

European Commission | Horizon 2020 European Union funding for Research & Innovation

Figure 1: Programme for day two of the event (01.12.2023)

Programme 30.11.2023

Welcome
09:45-10:00
Ralf Lindner, Fraunhofer ISI
Irina Elena Tiron, REA

Setting the scene
10:00-10:45
Danielle Shanley, Maastricht University

History and learnings
10:45-11:30
Moderation by Gema Revuelta,
University of Pompeu Fabra (UPF):
Ralf Lindner, Fraunhofer ISI
Thomas Kjedadger Ryan, Aarhus University
Shauna Stack, IHS
Carolina Llorente, UPF
Anestis Amanatidis, CWTS

Super MoRRI exhibition
11:30-12:30
PROMISE Portal
André Brasil, Leiden University
Thomas Kjedadger Ryan, Aarhus University
Case studies
Erich Griessler, Institute for Advanced Studies
Shauna Stack, Institute for Advanced Studies
Self-assessment tool
Steven Flipse, TU Delft
Emad Yaghmaei, TU Delft
Individual researcher survey
Hendrik Berghaeuser, Fraunhofer ISI
Susanne Bühner-Topçu, Fraunhofer ISI

Lunch: 12:00-13:30

World Café
11:30-12:30
Moderated by Ingeborg Meijer, CWTS:
Angela Simone, Mika Nieminen &
Carmen Fenollosa: REINFORCING
Stephane Berghmans: EUA
Fereshteh Rafieian: UNESCO
Ângela Guimarães Pereira: JRC (DEMOS)
Erzsébet Toth Czifra: CoARA

Break: 15:30-15:45

Reflections & check-out
15:45-16:00
Roger Strand, University of Bergen
Ângela Guimarães Pereira, JRC (DEMOS)

Parallel:
16:00 - open workspace
16:00 - drinks

Access the digital guide:

 Scientific Understanding
and Provision of an
Enhanced and Robust
Monitoring system for
RRI (SUPER MoRRI)

Figure 2: Programme for day one of the event (30.11.2023)

5.3. SUPER MoRRI Final Event Interactive Booklet

The booklet can be downloaded via following link. Please find below exemplary screenshots:
https://super-morri.eu/download/178/annual-events/5533/sumo_digital_leaflet.pdf

Figure 3: Example pages from the SUPER MoRRI digital leaflet

SUPER MoRRI

Scientific Understanding and Provision of an Enhanced and Robust Monitoring system for RRI Horizon 2020, Science with and for Society Work Programme 2018-2020, Topic: SwafS-21-2018 Grant Agreement Number: 824671

